

Knowledge Impact in the Global Innovation Index

Angelo Leogrande *°

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

The variable "Knowledge Impact" in the context of the Global Innovation Index (GII) measures the effect that innovation and the knowledge generated have on the economy and society. It is an indicator that evaluates how the results of research, technology, and innovation concretely influence the economic and social development of a country, going beyond the mere creation of new knowledge. It includes aspects such as the ability to transform research and development into products, services, and processes that generate added value. This variable focuses on elements such as the dissemination of knowledge, its impact on industrial sectors, and its ability to generate economic benefits through increased productivity and exports of high-tech goods and services. In essence, Knowledge Impact indicates how effectively a country can leverage innovation to improve its economic performance and create a favorable environment for sustainable growth. In the GII, this variable is fundamental to understanding how innovation is not limited to the ideation or development phase but extends to its concrete use, contributing to general well-being, international competitiveness, and technological progress. The data refer to the period between 2013 and 2022.

Knowledge Impact in 2022. The data on Knowledge Impact for 2022, part of the Global Innovation Index, show an interesting distribution across different countries in terms of how innovation and generated knowledge translate into concrete economic and social effects. Observing global performances, Estonia, with a score of 55.5, leads the ranking, followed by economic powers such as the United States (55) and China (52.8), which share the score with Italy. This highlights how even a relatively small country like Estonia can outperform nations with larger economies when it comes to fully utilizing knowledge to generate impact. It is interesting to note that traditionally innovative countries like Switzerland (51.3) and the United Kingdom (50.8) rank behind Estonia and the United States, suggesting that the effectiveness with which knowledge is transferred into economic results can vary regardless of technological development or the amount of resources invested in research. Singapore (50), another global innovation hub, also shows a relatively high score, demonstrating its ability to translate knowledge into economic impact despite the country's small size. In the middle of the ranking are European countries like Romania (48.6), Hungary (48.4), and Slovakia (48.2), which, although not among the top, show a decent ability to use innovation to stimulate economic growth. The Czech Republic (48) follows closely, while countries like Denmark (44.5), which is often ranked highly in other innovation indices, are slightly lower here. This may suggest that, despite a solid innovative ecosystem, not all countries can directly translate knowledge into economic impact. Nordic countries like Sweden (43.7), Ireland (44.4), and Finland (40.3), traditionally well-positioned in innovation rankings, show a slight misalignment compared to their Knowledge Impact potential, possibly due to less effective technology transfer and industrial application dynamics. Similarly, Germany (40.2), one of the world's strongest and most technologically advanced economies, does not rank among the top positions, indicating a challenge in converting innovation into widespread

economic impact. Emerging countries like South Korea (42.1) and China (52.8) demonstrate strong knowledge impact, highlighting how these economies can best utilize research and development results to enhance their global competitiveness. In particular, the fact that China has a similar score to Italy and higher than Switzerland reflects the significant investment that the country has made in technology and innovation. Among countries with lower scores, there are developing nations or those with less diversified economies, such as Vietnam (34.8), Turkey (34.9), and India (30.4), which, despite making significant progress in innovation, struggle to achieve proportional economic impact. African and South American nations like Kenya (21.6), Peru (22.5), and Ethiopia (21.6) rank among the lowest, highlighting structural and infrastructural difficulties that prevent the effective use of innovative resources. In general, these data show that Knowledge Impact does not solely depend on the amount of knowledge produced or investment in research and development but also on the ability to turn innovation into tangible and lasting results, such as increased productivity, economic competitiveness, and improved quality of life.

Knowledge Impact Between 2013 and 2022. The Global Innovation Index (GII) represents a measure of the innovative potential of countries, including several factors such as the ability to translate knowledge into economic outcomes. The data related to "Knowledge Impact" highlight the evolution of various countries' ability to transform innovation into tangible impacts on the economy and society between 2013 and 2022. The comparison between these years reveals very different trends, with some countries showing remarkable growth, while others experienced significant decline. Some of the countries with the most marked growth include African nations like Côte d'Ivoire (+2814.29%) and Guinea (+900%), alongside emerging countries like Rwanda (+518.52%) and Mongolia (+344%). This increase can be attributed to targeted development policies and investments in education and technological infrastructures, which have stimulated innovation. In particular, Côte d'Ivoire moved from a very low score (0.7 in 2013) to a significantly higher level (20.4 in 2022), indicating a notable improvement in its ability to generate and apply innovative knowledge. Rwanda is a significant example of how innovation can be a crucial factor for economic and social growth. In recent years, the country has invested heavily in digital technologies and education, allowing for significant growth in knowledge impact, reflected in an increase of over 500 percentage points. Countries like Panama (+106.90%), Tunisia (+33.67%), and Luxembourg (+25.00%) have shown more moderate but still positive growth. These countries have likely reached a level of innovation maturity but continue to benefit from steady investments in key areas such as higher education, scientific research, and technological infrastructures. Tunisia, despite being a North African country, has a tradition of innovation in the technological sector, enabling continued growth. On the contrary, some countries have seen a sharp decline in their knowledge impact. Notable examples include nations like Ghana (-64.21%), Mozambique (-73.89%), and Angola (-87.76%). These declines can be attributed to various factors, including political instability, lack of investment in technological infrastructures, and a struggling educational system. The situation in Angola, with a drastic reduction of 87.76%, indicates a significant deterioration in the country's ability to produce and apply innovations, likely due to economic and political challenges. Even more advanced economies such as Spain (-22.72%) and Germany (-14.65%) have seen a decrease in their knowledge impact. This could reflect a phase of stagnation or difficulty in maintaining high levels of innovation in an increasingly competitive global economic environment. In general, the data reveal a growing polarization between developing countries, many of which are improving their ability to innovate, and more advanced nations that are facing challenges in maintaining their leadership in innovation. The reasons behind these trends are complex and involve economic, political, and social factors, but the key to sustainable growth remains investment in education, research, and technological development.

Conclusions. The average Knowledge Impact value decreased between 2013 and 2022 across the countries considered, from 33.80 units to 27.86 units, representing a drop of -17.57%. The top performers, or countries where the Knowledge Impact value grew significantly between 2013 and 2022, include Côte d'Ivoire (+2814.29%), Guinea (+900.00%), Rwanda (+518.52%), Mongolia (+344.00%), and Togo (+220.00%). The worst performers, or countries where the Knowledge Impact value declined between 2013 and 2022, include Mali (-63.78%), Ghana (-64.12%), Mozambique (-73.89%), Yemen (-86.30%), and Angola (-87.67%).

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Appendix

Performance	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var per
Best Performers	Cote d'Ivoire	0,7	20,4	19,7	2814,29
	Guinea	0,2	2	1,8	900,00
	Rwanda	2,7	16,7	14	518,52
	Mongolia	2,5	11,1	8,6	344,00
	Togo	1,5	4,8	3,3	220,00
Worse Performers	Mali	37	13,4	-23,6	-63,78
	Ghana	44,7	16	-28,7	-64,21
	Mozambique	45,2	11,8	-33,4	-73,89
	Yemen, Rep.	7,3	1	-6,3	-86,30
	Angola	29,4	3,6	-25,8	-87,76